

PML

Plymouth Marine
Laboratory

Research excellence supporting a sustainable ocean

Constructing Digital Environments; Generating FAIR data from high resolution sensors in the Western Channel Observatory

Architecture design & requirements
elicitation workshop

29th March 2023 | v1.1

1st External Workshop; Overview

This workshop aims to facilitate an informal exchange of ideas about the Western Channel Observatory (WCO) Constructing Digital Environments (CDE) project. The workshop will provide:

An update of the project status and key tasks.

- *Including an analysis of each of the planned development elements against the GoFair principles.*

A demonstration of the sprint 1 **data visualisation** minimum viable product (MVP)

- *The demonstration aims to articulate the concept, prompt discussion and elicit feedback that will drive the second development sprint activities.*

A Demonstration of the sprint 1 **data request & ticketing** MVP

- *The demonstration aims to articulate the concept, prompt discussion and elicit feedback that will drive the second development sprint activities.*

A recap of discussion highlights and a summary of the potential next steps.

Progress Update; Project Overview

- 6 month project
- £42 K
- Due to complete 31st July 2023

- Agile development of 2 main areas
 - Data visualisation and preview
 - Data request ticketing

Progress Update; Project aims and objectives

- As stated in the project proposal, the aims and objectives of this project are:

Progress Update; How will the planned activities increase the FAIRness of WCO data?

GoFair Principles	GoFair Definition	Relevance to this CDE project	
Findable	The first step in (re)using data is to find them. Metadata and data should be easy to find for both humans and computers. Machine-readable metadata are essential for automatic discovery of datasets and services, so this is an essential component of the FAIRification process.	●	Project activities focus on making the data and metadata more intuitive to human users during at the data preview and initial data analysis phase. Specifically, users will be able to interact with data from multiple sensors in linked plots. In addition, the visibility of the metadata will be increased, encouraging the creation and review of metadata early in the product lifecycle. This project will also begin the process of standardising and structuring the data requires process. While there will still be humans in the loop at the end of this project, the work in this project will build the foundations required for future, automated data discovery.
Accessible	Once the user finds the required data, she/he/they need to know how they can be accessed, possibly including authentication and authorisation.	🕒	Project activities include the clear structuring of recent data, with persistent URLs provided to the emerging data products.
Interoperable	The data usually needs to be integrated with other data. In addition, the data need to interoperate with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing.	🌐	Tools will be provided that encourage researchers to explore and combine data from multiple sensors with linked tools that allow the initial scientific analysis of multiple data sets. Data request workflows will also be documented and formalised.
Reusable	The ultimate goal of FAIR is to optimise the reuse of data. To achieve this, metadata and data should be well-described so that they can be replicated and/or combined in different settings.	●	Increasing the visibility of the metadata is a core concept in the long-term plan to improve its quality and coverage. By developing tools that highlight missing or non-standardised metadata from the early stages of the data pipeline, a light will be shone into the metadata, supporting the principle of <i>creating metadata once</i> .

Data Visualisations; Current WCO Tools

Intro & workshop aims

Project progress update

Demo Data Viz. MVP

Develop Ticketing MVP

Discussion & next steps

Western Channel Observatory

NERC National Capability of the Plymouth Marine Laboratory and Marine Biological Association

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L4 in-situ data station

These data are collected using sensors attached to our sampling rosette, by the R/V Plymouth Quest, at station L4 which is [located](#) 10 nautical miles south-west of Plymouth. The sensors include a SeaBird SBE 19+, a transmissometer, a Chelsea PAR sensor, a fluorometer and an oxygen optode. These data form part of a long time series collected at this station and are included in the [ICES Report on Ocean Climate](#). The entire time-series can be downloaded [here](#). To use these data please contact [James Fishwick](#). Additional date, time and instrument number information is also [available](#)

Data plots for 20/03/2023

<h4 style="text-align: center; margin: 0;">Temperature (°C)</h4>	<h4 style="text-align: center; margin: 0;">Salinity (PSU)</h4>
<h4 style="text-align: center; margin: 0;">Density (kgm⁻³)</h4>	<h4 style="text-align: center; margin: 0;">Fluorescence (no unit)</h4>

Data Visualisations; Sprint 1 Updates

Data Visualisations; Updates in the last 10 minutes 😊

Data Request Ticketing; Sprint 1 Update

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Step 1
Find the subset of data that you'd like

Parameter names and POCs

ID	Parameter	Unit	Start Date	End Date	Depth (m)	POC
1	Temperature	°C	2011-01-01	2011-01-31	0-10	John
2	Salinity	PSU	2011-01-01	2011-01-31	0-10	John
3	Chlorophyll a	µg/L	2011-01-01	2011-01-31	0-10	John
4	Chlorophyll b	µg/L	2011-01-01	2011-01-31	0-10	John
5	Chlorophyll c	µg/L	2011-01-01	2011-01-31	0-10	John
6	Chlorophyll d	µg/L	2011-01-01	2011-01-31	0-10	John
7	Chlorophyll e	µg/L	2011-01-01	2011-01-31	0-10	John
8	Chlorophyll f	µg/L	2011-01-01	2011-01-31	0-10	John
9	Chlorophyll g	µg/L	2011-01-01	2011-01-31	0-10	John
10	Chlorophyll h	µg/L	2011-01-01	2011-01-31	0-10	John

Step 2
Submit the auto-completed request form

The screenshot shows a web form titled "Western Channel Observatory" with a navigation bar (Home, Data, Publications, Webcams, About us, Contact us). The form is a "Custom Data Request Form" and includes sections for "User Details" (Name, Email, Organisation), "Data Details" (Start Date, End Date), "Measurement" (CTD, Molecular Data, Benthic Survey, Zooplankton), "Site" (L4, E1, Quest), and "Additional Details" (a text area for additional information). There are "Reset" and "Submit" buttons at the bottom.

Step 2.a
Request written to log

Step 2.b
Automated email sent to data POCs

Recap; Sprint 1 progress against project objectives

- As stated in the project proposal, the aims and objectives of this project are:

Project objective	Measure of success	Tom's Sprint 1 Progress-o-meter	Notes
Objective 1	The visualisation tools should include an intuitive representation of key metadata values.	●	Standards-based metadata displayed during the data discovery, preview and initial analysis stages.
	External users shall be prompted to select start dates, end dates and variable(s) of interest via embedded widgets to create a visualisation of available data.	●	Interactive tools embedded into the development website. Tool to be applied to the time-separated composite data in future development sprints.
	External users shall be guided through the data download process, using parameters configured in the drawing regions of the plot.	●	Interactive tools embedded into the development website and data request page created. Links between them to be developed in future sprints.
Objective 2	External users shall be prompted to fill in all details of the request form and submit a data request. External users should be prompted to tag any suspected data quality issues against a subset of data.	●	Details emerging from the internal impact and data provision team workshops developed. Tools that allow issues to be reported to be added in future sprints.
	A database shall record requests so impact analyses may be made.	●	Data request details logged in a central database and automated emails sent to POCs. Future activities to ensure that the automated architecture can be scaled and expanded.
	The data request form shall auto-populate based on current selections made within the data visualisation tools (Objective 1). Data stewards shall be automatically notified, based on the variables of interest that are selected in the form.	●	Automated emails send to POCs. Links between visualisation and data request tools to be developed in future sprints.

Recap

- Key discussion points and activities raised in this workshop
 - Record to be made here at the end of the workshop

Recap

- Next steps
 - Development Sprint 2 due to start
 - Would a 2nd workshop be useful at the start of May?
 - Providing a chance for us to develop / prototype the ideas discussed today and validate our understanding.

Thanks for your time!